

A study on the interactions between the Universe and Earth (Irlapatism-A New Hypothetical Model of Cosmology)

Author Details: Gangadhara Rao Irlapati

H.No.5-30-4/1, Saibabanagar, Jeedimetla, Hyderabad - 500 055, Telangana, India.

email: gangadhar19582058@gmail.com

Abstract: *There is a relation between the gravitational forces and changes in the Earth. Everyone should know about the origin, structure, nature, evolution of the universe and its various properties. Since, all the hazards on the earth directly or indirectly are associated with the gravitational forces of the universe. Further, this in order to be study the hazards, study of the cosmology is needed to know about hazards. There are hazards on the earth, on other planets and there are also happening within atoms. Human beings are on the earth, are on the outside planets of the earth and also on the neutrons in the atoms. Even if the world's people appreciate or criticize me, it is fact. Hazards caused by asteroids, meteoroids, and comets as they pass near the earth, enter the earth's atmosphere, and /or strike the earth, and by changes in inter planetary ionosphere, and atmosphere. In the face of extra-terrestrial hazards and events that can lead to disasters, it is important to live in a resilient community because these types of disasters are so unpredictable and depending on the size of meteorite can cause serious damage through the heat emitted during impacts with earth's surface .In addition , impact can cause earth quakes , Tsunami, wildfires ,acid ,rains from nitrogen oxides, darkness from dust and soot and global warming. It is for this reason that staying aware and prepared at all times is extra important. This is not an implication to live in fear, but a reminder to stay educated about these types of disasters and to have a plan in place as with any other type of disaster. Before an extraterrestrial hazards /events occur, there are some steps that can be taken to mitigate and minimize the impact. I have conducted many studies on the universe and its extra-terrestrial hazards and gravitational forces and its effect on the natural hazards on the earth. A new hypothetical model of cosmology will helpful to study and know the universe, extra-terrestrial hazards and gravitational forces and its effect on the natural hazards on the earth. During the period of 1970-77, many researches and studies have done by me on the origin, nature structure and evolution of the cosmos and its relation between the gravitational forces and changes in the Earth and proposed A New Hypothetical Model of Cosmology with hundreds of basic facts. Some things are yet to be explained.*

Key Words: Irlapatism,A New Hypothetical Model of Cosmology.

Introduction:

The cosmos is made up of universes in infinite number, having similar structure and properties, embedded one in each other and extended in ascending and descending order. To explain and justify this model, there are three universes so far known to us (a) Geo-Universe (b) Atomic-Universe (c) Energy-Universe. These three are having similar structure and properties, embedded one in each other and extended in ascending and descending order. Of these three, we known some extent about the internal structure and properties of the Geo-Universe but we do not known its external structure. We know some extent about the external structure and properties of the Energy-Universe but we do not know its internal structure. Between of these three universes, we came to know a large extent about the internal &

external structure and properties of the Atomic-Universe. Hence, I have taken the similarities of external structure & properties between the Geo-Universe & Atomic-Universe to propose that all the universes in ascending and descending order of the creation are having similar internal structure and properties. The similarities of external structure & properties between the Atomic Universe and Energy-Universe are taken to propose that all the universe in ascending and descending order of creation are having similar external structure and properties. And the manner in which of these three universes i.e., embedded one in each other, extended in ascending and descending order to propose that all the universes in ascending and descending order of the creation are embedded one in each other and extended in ascending and descending order.

Similar External Structure & Properties

According to the model, all the universes in ascending and descending order of the creation are having similar external structure and properties. To justify this, I have taken many similarities between the atom and photon.

For example:-

Atomic-Universe	Energy-Universe
1) The atom appearing in several forms such as Hydrogen to uranium etc., being due to the Internal structure having different atomic particles at various numbers	2) The particle “Photon” related to energy appearing in several forms such as radio waves, gamma rays, violet rays etc being may be probably due to the internal structure having different particles at various numbers.
2)The atom exhibiting several physical and chemical Properties such as weight, colour, taste, hardness etc being due to the internal structure having different particles at various number.)The particle “photon” related to energy exhibiting properties such as wave length colour, temperature etc being may be Probably due to the internal structure having different particles at various number.

SIMILAR INTERNAL STRUCTURE & PROPERTIES

According to the model, all the universes in ascending and descending order of the creation are having similar internal structure and properties. To explain and justify this, I have taken the many similarities between the atomic-universe and Geo-Universe.

Atomic-Universe	Geo-Universe
1)Various atomic particles at different sizes in several numbers are present in the atom	1) Various astronomical objects at different sizes in several numbers are present in the Geo- Universe
2) These atomic particles having three types of charges at negative, positive and neutral states are present in the atom	2) These astronomical objects having three type of charges at positive, negative and neutral states are present in the Geo- Universe
3) Positively charged protons are present in the nucleus	3) Stars built by atoms having positive charged nucleus are present in centre of the Geo-Universe
4) Neutrons at neutral state are present in the Nucleus.	4) Planets at neutral state are present in Centre of the Geo – Universe
5) Negatively charged electrons are present at large distance of the atomic nucleus in the atom	5) Here is a concept that anti-matter cosmic bodies built by atoms having negatively charged nucleus are present at large distance of the Geo-Universe.
6) Additional neutrons called isotopes are present.	6) Additional planets called satellites around the planets are present
7) Radiation emitting from the atom.	7) Cosmic rays emitting from the Geo- Universe.
8) There is a property of nuclear fission is in the atom.	8) There is a property of super Nova is in the Geo -Universe.

Descending Order Of Creation:

The Geo-Universe that means the Universe seen around our earth is having magnificent structure and properties such as galaxies, stars and planets and some planets such as earth having continents, countries, oceans, trees, animals. Cyclones, human beings etc. Such Geo-Universe being built by Universes of its descending order of creation that means atoms.

Atomic-Universe that means the atom present in several forms from hydrogen to uranium etc is another universe having magnificent structure and properties such as electrons, protons, neutrons, etc., and continents, countries, oceans, cyclones, trees, animals, human beings may be present on some neutrons having suitable conditions exactly similar to the earth planet resembling to the Geo-Universe. Such atomic Universe being built by universes of its descending order of creation that means energy particle ‘photons’.

The Energy-Universe that means the particle “photon” related to energy present in several forms of electromagnetic radiation is also another universe having magnificent structure and properties resembling to Geo-Universe and atom. Such Energy-Universe may also being built by Universes of its descending order of creation that is not yet known to us.

Thus the descending order of creation continuous infinitely.

Ascending Order Of Creation:

The Energy-universe that means the particle related to energy “photon” having magnificent structure and properties is being as a primary syntactic unit in the universe of its ascending order of creation that means atom. All components in the atom are built by these “photons” in infinite number. Such each and every energy particle “photon” is basis to an infinite descending order of creation.

The Atomic—Universe that means the “Atom” having magnificent structure and properties is being as a primary

syntactic unit in the universe of its ascending order of creation that means in our Geo-Universe. All components in the Geo-Universe such as stars, planets etc., are built by these atoms in infinite number. Such each and every atom is basis to an infinite descending order of creation.

The Geo-Universe that means the “Universe” seen around our earth having magnificent structure and properties is being as a primary syntactic unit in the universe of its ascending order of creation that is not yet known to us. All components in that Universe are built by these Geo-Universes in infinite number. Such each and every Geo-Universe in that ascending creation is basis to an infinite descending order of creation.

Thus the ascending order of creation continuous infinite.

Extraterrestrial hazards:

Everyone should know about the origin, structure, nature, evolution of the universe and its various properties. Since, all the hazards on the earth directly or indirectly are associated with the gravitational forces of the universe. Further, this in order to be study the hazards, study of the cosmology is needed to know about hazards. There are hazards on the earth, on other planets and there are also happening within atoms. Human beings are on the earth, are on the outside planets of the earth and also on the neutrons in the atoms. Even if the world’s people appreciate or criticize me, it is fact. Hazards caused by asteroids, meteoroids ,and comments as they pass near the earth ,enter the earth’s atmosphere ,and /or strike the earth ,and by changes in inter planetary ionosphere, and atmosphere. In the face of extra terrestrial hazards and events that can lead to disasters, it is important to live in a resilient community because these types of disasters are so unpredictable and depending on the size of meteorite can cause serious damage through the heat emitted during impacts with earth’s surface .In addition , impact can cause earth quakes , Tsunami, wildfires ,acid ,rains from nitrogen oxides, darkness from dust and soot and global warming. It is for this reason that staying aware and prepared at all times is extra important. This is not an implication to live in fear, but a reminder to stay educated about these types of disasters and to have a plan in place as with any other type of disaster. Before an extraterrestrial hazards /events occur, there are some steps that can be taken to mitigate and minimize the impact. I have conducted many studies on the universe and its extra terrestrial hazards and gravitational forces and its affect on the natural hazards on the earth. A new hypothetical model of cosmology will helpful to study and know the universe, extra terrestrial hazards and gravitational forces and its affect on the natural hazards on the earth.

The impact of the gravitational forces on Earth’s atmosphere:

The year to year change of movement of axis of the earth inclined at 23½ degrees from vertical to its path around the sun does play a significant role on the Earth’s atmosphere and stimulates the weather. The inter-tropical convergence zone at

the equator follows the movement of the sun and shifts north of the equator merges with the heat low pressure zone created by the rising heat of the sub-continent due to direct and converging rays of the summer sun on the India Sub-Continent and develops into the monsoon trough and maintain monsoon circulation.

Cosmic-Environments:

The fill of structure and characteristics in the universe of the cosmos proposed as **cosmic environments**. For example the fill of structure and characteristics like galaxies, stars, planets etc in the Geo-Universe proposed as Geo-Environment, the fill of structure and characteristics like proton, neutrons and electrons etc in the Atomic-Universe proposed as Atomic-Environment and the fill of structure and characteristics in the Energy-Universe that means in the photon that is not yet known proposed as Energy-Environment.

Space Weather:

The fill of structure and characteristics like galaxies, Stars, Planets and their orbits and other physical forces etc that surrounds in the universe proposed as space atmosphere, the state of galaxies, stars, planets, nebulas. Pulsars etc at a particular region over a long period of time proposed as space-climate, the state of characteristics of space- climate like solar wind flares, asteroids etc at a particular region during a short period of time proposed as space-weather.

Space Regions:

The state of space atmosphere being in still proposed as “Inactive Space Region”, the state of space atmosphere being in active proposed as “Active Space Region” The region of space atmosphere in which the celestial bodies are more widespread areas proposed as “Space High Pressure Area” the less widespread areas proposed as “ Space Low Pressure Area”.

Space Low Pressure Systems:

Some space times happens variation of differences of pressure in the space-climate, At such a juncture, the celestial bodies and other space dust present in the space high pressure area will try to occupy the space low pressure area all at once. In this attempt, they will whirl around the space low pressure. The centre of space low pressure area itself is the black-hole and the circular whirling celestial bodies & other space dust etc caused by the space low pressure area proposed as Galaxy.

Studies Carried Out: Many studies were carried out on this Hypothesis and it was successfully proved out in the studies.

Appeal:

I humbly request the world scientists and people to recognise me as the ORIGINATOR OF THE THEORY OF IRLAPATISM-A NEW HYPOTHETICAL MODEL OF COSMOLOGY and specify in your research papers by making a reference of discoveries and inventions and bring me into light.

I appeal the world scientists that if the world scientists acquire the science&technology of recreation of organism to recreate the pass away people in future, please remember and recreate me to complete my incompleted goal & ideal.

Conclusion:

I would like to have an extensive discussion on my hypothesis. My theory is the basic relating to the cosmology. Many things that visible to researchers relating to beyond the extreme deep intergalactic space and expanding universe etc are yet to be explained.

Acknowledgements:

I am grateful to Sri Hong who has given valuable advice in this research. Ther was also taken some information from the Wikipedia.,I am grateful to them.

Invention history: I have conducted many studies on the origin, nature structure and evolution of the universe during the 1970-77 and proposed a new Hypothetical model of cosmology with hundreds or postulations. In 1977, a book was published in the name of IRLAPATISM-IRLAPTATI THEORY OF UNIVERSE on the basis of the postulations of the hypothesis by the supporters. The postulations about the universe, existence of god, theory of evolution etc in the book were exposed to the anger of fanatic people and I got into a violent altercation about these postulations of the hypothesis. As a result I was subjected to the suppressions and persecutions. I reported these suppressions and torments to the revenue divisional officer. Amalapuram on 6-7-1977 the revenue divisional officer was conducted an enquiry about this matter on forenoon, July 21st, 1977 while returning from the enquiry, I was attacked by a mob and they had taken me to the village chavadi. Followed by an altercation with tortures about the theory, they beaten and f forced me to put signatures on some false documents, and an offence falsely framed and foisted against me. After that I was sent to the taluk magistrate, kothapeta for another trial with the investigation of the superstitions, the taluk magistrate was declared me as a dangerous boy and up to anything and issued sentence to punish me and handed over to the police station, ravulapalem. The police was arrested me on July 21, 1977 registered a case and sent to remand, I was kept imprisoned some months in subjail and remaining period interrogated periodically by panatics and officers. The trials were done between April 2, 1979 to November 20,1979 after trials, the Honble Additional Judicial First Class Magistrate court was found me not guilty and acquitted on November 27,1979.

Inventor biography:

Gangadhara Rao Irlapati born on 25,May,1958 at Merlpalem Village in India to pullaiah irlapati and manikyam irlapati. He has acquired all sciences inherently by birth. However, he completed his primary classes 1 to 5 in elementary school, Merlapalem(1963-1968),upper primary classes 6&7 in upper primary school, Vubalanka (1969-1971), High School classes 8 to 10 in Zilla Parishad High school, Ravulapalem(1971-

1974), and junior college education 11&12 in Mahatma junior college, Atryapuram(1974-1976).He did his graduation B.A in economic sciences etc in Andhra university(1985-1989) and post-graduation M.Sc in disaster mitigation sciences in Sikkim Manipal University, Gangtok(2001-2003).

He is a science enthusiast and experimenter with an ideal to serve the people from the weather canges and natural hazards and submitted many representations to the government research organizations for providing research facilities but the government and research organizations did not encourage and provide research opportunities to him. He was envied by Research Institutes, scientists and subjected to incessant verbal insults. He built a lab at his house with available apparatus and books and conducted thousands of researches on weather problems and natural calamities and made hundreds of research papers on weather problems and natural hazards. He invented the Lisposcope, Biolumicells and Bio-forecast In 1967. proposed A New Hypothetical Model of Cosmolgy in 1977. designed the Geoscope in 1989. invented the Indian Monsoon Time Scale in 1991. Mainly he did a lot of work into the design of the Global Monsoon Time Scales and Geoscope projects for the various regions of the world.

However much efforts did tho, he could not get recognition either by government or by society moreover ridiculed and subjected in many ways. Mainly the revolutionary and rational concepts about the cosmology were instantly criticized and exposed to the anger of superstitious, got into violent altercations. He was arrested, tortured and imprisoned. Research organizations and Officials were humiliated him in different ways. His efforts have been criticized. Political recommendations, officials support, publicity, region, religion, cash and community factors may influence in giving recognition, awards, rewards, honor and fame to dalit scientists in India. He is a victim of negligence. racism and discrimination. Now he is in severe crisis, making his life's last journey due to pains & poverty and disregard & despair..

References:

- 1) Cover page of the book IRLAPATISM-IRLAPTATI THEORY OF UNIVERSE was published on 1st july,1977 by the supporters.
- 2) Report to the Revenue Divisional Officer. Amalapuram on 6-7-1977 about persecutions and torments of the fanatic people.
- 3) Orders of the Taluk Magistrate, kothapeta A-2-5873/77 Dt. 21-07-77 Taluk Office, Kothapeta declared him as a dangerous boy and up to anything and issued sentence to punish him and handed over to the police station, Ravulapalem.
- 4) He was arrested by the police on July 21, 1977. A case was registered C.No.53/77 and he was remanded.

- 5) The Judgment of the Hon'ble Additional Judicial First Class Magistrate Court, Kothapeta C.C.No. 13/79 in which he was found not guilty and acquitted on November 27,1979.

- 6) Calendar and Judgment C.C.No. 13/79 of the Court of the Judicial Magistrate of the 1 Class,Kothapeta.

Corresponding Author:

Gangadhara Rao Irlapati
H.No.5-30-4/1,
Saibabanagar,Jeedimetla
Hyderabad, Telangana-500055, India

APPENDICIES:

Telephone: xxx-xxx-xxxx

E-mail: gangadhar19582058@gmail.com

Wiki:

Psychometric assessment. (n.d.). Retrieved from [http://psychology.wikia.com/wiki/psychometric assesmrnt](http://psychology.wikia.com/wiki/psychometric_assesmrnt).

Phonological Appendes:

The Appendes that describe the contents are enclosed.

Historical events supported documents:

The documents that supports the events in the history of the invention are enclosed

Geo- Universe has its own structure and properties exactly similar to the structure and properties resembling Atom and Energy particle. There are stars, planets, galaxies and life on the earth etc. present in the Geo- Universe.

Atom is gigantic Universe having structure and properties exactly similar to the structure and properties resembling our Geo-Universe. and Energy particle. Just as there are stars, planets, galaxies and life on the earth etc. present in the Geo-Universe, in the same way exactly similar stars, planets, galaxies and life on neutrons etc. may be present in the form of electrons, protons and neutrons in the atom.

Energy particle has internal structure and having three kinds of basic elements proposed and named as Positive energions (PEONS) Negative energions (NEONS) and Neutral energions (NEUONS), it is also another universe named as Energy- Universe having structure and properties exactly similar to the structure and properties resembling our Geo- Universe and Atomic- Universe.

Geo-UNIVERSE has its own structure and properties exactly similar to the structure and properties resembling Atom and Energy particle. There are stars, planets, galaxies and life on the earth etc. present in the Geo-UNIVERSE.

Energy particle has [Atomic] structure and having three kinds of basic elements proposed and named as Positive energies (PEONS) Negative energies (NEONS) and Neutral energies (NEUCONS). It is also another universe named as Energy-UNIVERSE having structure and properties exactly similar to the structure and properties resembling our Geo-UNIVERSE and Atomic-UNIVERSE.

Atom is gigantic UNIVERSE having structure and properties exactly similar to the structure and properties resembling our Geo-UNIVERSE and Energy particle. Just as there are stars, planets, galaxies and life on the earth etc. present in the Geo-UNIVERSE, in the same way exactly similar stars, planets, galaxies and life on neutrons etc. may be present in the form of electrons, protons and neutrons in the atom.

IRLAPATISM

Irlapati Theory of Universe

G. R. IRLAPATI.

మహారాజశే, రెవినయ్య డివిజనల్ ఆఫీసరు
వారి దివ్యసముఖమునకు,
అమలాపురం.

తూర్పుగోదావరి జిల్లా, కొత్తవేట లాలాకా మెర్లపాలెం గ్రామకాపురస్తుడు ఇర్లపాటి
పుల్లయ్య కుమారుడు ఇర్లపాటి గంగాధరరావు అను నేను మిక్కిలి విదేయతో నమస్కరించి
దాఖలు చేసుకొను విన్నపములు.

అయ్యా,

నేను శాస్త్ర పరిశోధనలు చేసి దేశానికి నేమలు చేయాలనే ఆశయమును కలిగిన
శాస్త్రపరిశోధకుడను. ఇంటి వద్దనే చిన్న పరిశోధనాలయమును వెట్టుకొని ప్య యోగాలు చేసు
కొంటున్నాను. సుష్టి ఆపిరావము, నిర్మాణము, ధర్మాలు, పరిణామము మాననసుష్టి మతము-
దైవము మొదలగు విషయాలను విశదీకరిస్తూ, వాదాలను ప్రతిపాదించాను & ఇటీకాకుండా
ప్రజలను తుఘ్నాలు, కర్పకాటకాలు, నరదలనంచి ప్ర కుత్తిమెపరీత్యాలనుండి కాపాడటానికిగాను
కొన్ని న్యాయాలను పద్మతులను జియోనోపు వంటి పరికరాలను రూపొందిస్తున్నాను. ఇంకా
అనేక శాస్త్రీయ ప్రచురణలు ప్రచారము ద్వారా నేవచేస్తున్నాను. అయితే మా గ్రామ కరణంగారు,
మునసబుగారు, ఆత్రేయపురం రెవినయ్య ఇన్స్పెక్టరుగారు, కొత్తవేట తహసీల్దారు గారు ఇతరులు
మూఢనమ్మకాలతో నా సిద్ధాంతాలను విమర్శిస్తూ, వాగ్వాదము చేస్తున్నారు. నా పరిశోధనలకు
ఆడ్డంకులు కలిగిస్తున్నారు. నాకు కులధర్మపత్యమున్న సంతకము వెట్టుకుండా బాదిస్తున్నారు.
దయతో ఈ విషయమై విచారించి నాకు రక్షణ కల్పించమని న్యాయము చేయుమని వేడుకొనుచున్నాను.

ఇటు, తమ విశ్వాసనీయుడు,

9 Gangadhara Reddy
6-7-77

: ఇర్లపాటి గంగాధరరావు

మెర్లపాలెం,
తే 6-7-1977

Received a tipped report Taluk Magistrate Kotta Peta with the following:-
 Ref. A-2-5873/77 dt 21-7-77 Taluk office Kotta Peta.

From: Sri P. Subbarao, C. Com. Taluk Magistrate To: The Station House Officer Ravulapalem.

Sir, Subj: Signature - Forgery Signature - Sri J. I. Gangadhara Rao of Nerlapalem V. Report of the Revenue Inspector - Atreyapuram.

Ref: Report of the Sr. Rev. Inspector, Atreyapuram dt 21-7-77.

The Rev. Inspector Atreyapuram enquired and reported that Smt. Relangi Rattamma wife of Muraliah of Nerlapalem village applied for grant of a tree (Tamarind) situated on the north-west portion of her house for which house - No. - Patta was granted. On the above petition the signatures of Village Munsiff, Nerlapalem and the Rev. Inspector, Atreyapuram were forged.

The Rev. Inspector, Atreyapuram further reported that Smt. Relangi Rattamma in her statement deposed that the second son of Sri J. I. Gangadhara Rao forged the signatures. As such the Rev. Inspector, Atreyapuram has called for the individual and examined in to the matter and reported that he failed Intermediate and left hand - writer. He accepted that he forged signatures and the resolutions of the Village Munsiff, Nerlapalem and the Rev. Inspector, Atreyapuram. He is a very dangerous boy and is up to any thing.

In the above case since Sri J. I. Gangadhara Rao of Muraliah of Nerlapalem village, the offender in the instant case may be dealt with according to law. Please intimate the action taken in the matter.

1. The following records are enclosed here with duty officiating officer and in closed form.

2. Slip containing forged Signature.

3. Statement recorded from Sri J. I. Gangadhara Rao of Muraliah of Nerlapalem village.

4. Statement of Smt. Relangi Rattamma wife of Muraliah of Nerlapalem village.

5. Report of the Rev. Inspector, Atreyapuram dated 21-7-77.

6. The offender is produced before you through the Rev. Inspector Atreyapuram for taking in to custody.

Encl: - As stated above.
 (sd, P. Ramasastri)
 Head clerk.

yours faithfully,
 (sd, P. Subbarao)
 Taluk - Magistrate
 Kotta Peta.

Copy Submitted to the collector, Kakinada.
 Copy Submitted Superior In-charge of Police, Kakinada,
 Copy to the Rev. Divl. Officer - Amalapuram,
 Copy to the Circle Inspector of Police - Amalapuram.

To the
Jahaidan }
Kotha-Peta } -26-

Sir I registered the above as C.No 53/44 U/S 420,
467, and 471 g.c. and copies of F.I.Rs submitted to all
concerned officers and original F.I.R were sent to J.F.C Magistrate
Kotha-peta.

(S) K.N. Murthy Sub- H.C. 1635-
S.D.
Ravalapalem. 21. 7. 77

" True copy "

[Signature]
H.C. 1635
S.D. Ravalapalem

28

IN THE COURT OF THE JUDICIAL MAGISTRATE OF THE I CLASS KOTHAPETA.
PRESENT: SRI D. VENKATANARAYANA, B.Com., LL.B., Judicial Magistrate
of the I Class.

TUESDAY, the 27th day of November, 1979.

C.C.No. 13/79.

Between:

The State of Andhra Pradesh, through

The State Inspector of Police, Razole

Cr.No.53/79 of Ravulapalem P.S. .. Complainant.

and

Irlapati Gangadhara rao,
s/o Fullayya, Aged 19 yrs.
Merlapalem.

.. Accused.

This case coming on 20.11.79 for hearing before me in the presence of the State-Complainant and the accused appearing in person and having stood over for consideration till this day, the court delivered the following:-

JUDGMENT

The Inspector of Police, Razole has laid the charge sheet in Cr.No.53/79 of Ravulapalem Police Station Under Sections 420, and 471 IPC against the accused herein.

2. The case of the prosecution is that P.W.1 is resident of Merlapalem village and she is living in a house constructed in R.S.No.129 in Merlapalem village which was given to her by the Revenue Department. There is a tamarind tree in the said house site near her house. The branches of the said tree were over-hanging on her house endangering safety to her house. She was advised to apply for patta of the said tamarind tree. The accused who had come to know about it approached P.W.1 two weeks prior to 21.7.77 and offered his services to get the tree of patta for her and he induced her to affix her thumb impression on the application written by him and wanted her to get the recommendations of the Village Munsif and Revenue Inspector, Atreyapuram. When she expressed her inability to secure their signatures he resorted to forging of the signatures of Village Munsif, Merlapalem and Revenue Inspector (P.W.4). Completing the application and the recommendation

enforced for verification and enquiry on 21.7.77, contacted P.W. 1 to and also questioned the accused at the village chavidi of Ryali before whom the accused admitted the offence and P.W.4 recorded the statements of P.W.1 and the accused. The accused was produced before the Tahsildar, Kothapeta who forwarded the accused to the Police Station, Ravulapalem along with Exs.pl to p4 The police, Ravulapalem registered Cr.No.53/77 U/s. 420,467 and 471 IPC. Therefore, the accused is liable for punishment under sec. 420,467 and 471 IPC.

3. The case was taken on file against the accused Under sec. 420, 467 and 471 IPC. When the accused appeared before this court, copies of documents contemplated Under sec. 207 Cr.P.C. were furnished to him and he was examined on the contents of the documents. He denied the offence. On consideration of the documents, a charge Under sec. 420, 467 and 471 IPC were framed, readover, interpreted and explained to the accused in Telugu to which he pleaded not guilty and claimed to be tried.

4. The prosecution, in support of its case, examined P.W.1, who wanted to apply patta of the tamarind tree, P.W.2 the village Munsif, Ryali, P.W.3, Village Kannam of Ryali, P.W.4 the Revenue Inspector in whose presence the accused is alleged to have confessed the offence, P.W.5 the Head Constable who registered the crime. P.W.6 the Investigating Officer, P.W.7, the Tahsildar who forwarded the accused and report of P.W.4 to Ravulapalem P.S. and got marked Ex.pl to p6. The accused did not adduce any oral or documentary evidence.

5. After closure of the prosecution evidence, the accused was examined U/s. 313 Cr.P.C. regarding the incriminating circumstances appearing in the evidence of the prosecution against the accused. The plea of the accused is total denial of the offence. He stated that P.W.4 is superstitious and fanatic and that when P.W.4 was telling about God once he told him that human being was born from monkey. Therefore, P.W.4 grew wild in that connection

and that subsequently when he approached P.W.4 to sign on the caste certificate, he demanded Rs. 10/- from him and that subsequently he reported the matter to the Revenue Divisional Officer, Amalapuram about the demanding of illegal gratification of P.W.4. The R.D.O. Amalapuram has promised to enquire into the matter. Therefore, this case is falsely foisted against him. when he was coming from Ravulapalem the village servant took him before P.W.4. Thereafter he was ~~kept~~ taken to village chavidi where P.Ws. 1 to 4 were present and they beat him and obtained his signature on Ex.P3 and subsequently he was taken to the Pansildar, Kothapeta from there he was sent to Police Station, Ravulapalem and that he is innocent and he did not commit any offence.

6. The point for consideration is whether the prosecution has been able to establish its case against the accused, beyond all reasonable doubt?

7. The case of the prosecution is that the accused forged the signature of P.S.4 the Revenue Inspector and Village Munsif, Merlapalem (who is no more alive). Ex.P1 is the petition which contains the alleged forged signatures of Village Munsif, Merlapalem and Revenue Inspector (P.W.4). Ex.P1 is in torn condition. The alleged signature of Village Munsif, Merlapalem is completely torn and the signature of P.W.4 is also torn completely except some portion. It also contains the thumb impression alleged to have been affixed by P.W.1. The prosecution to establish that it is the accused who is responsible for the alleged forgery of signatures of P.W.4 and Village Munsif, Merlapalem relied on Ex.P1 petition and Ex.P2 the slip which is also alleged to have been signed by the accused in the presence of P.Ws. 2 to 4. There is no direct evidence available, in this case, who witnesses the forging of the signatures of P.W.4 and Village Munsif, Merlapalem. Even the alleged signatures are in torn condition. Regarding the statement of the accused recorded by P.W.4 in the presence

→ is that he was beaten by P.W.4 and others and he was forced to put his signature on Ex.P3 and also Ex.P2. Further, the
→ plea of the accused is that there was altercation between him
→ and P.W.4 with regard to the existence of God and also with regard to obtaining of signature of P.W.4 on the caste certificate. Except, the confession statement of the accused Ex.P3 before P.Ws. 2 to 4, there is no direct evidence to connect the accused with the offences charged against him. P.W.4 is an illiterate. She does not know on which paper the accused obtained her thumb impression. Even for a moment sake, it is presumed that it is the accused who obtained the signature of P.W.1, on Ex.P1, Ex.P1 itself is completely in torn condition and the Tahsildar, Kothapeta who is competent authority to grant patta of the tamarind tree, would not have acted upon the petition Ex.P1. Moreover, the prosecution failed to explain the reason why the accused forged the signature of P.W.4 and the Village Munsif, Merlapalem on Ex.P1 and by forging the signature what is the wrongful gain the accused wanted to obtain. There is no evidence to show that it is the accused who filed Ex.P1 petition and other enclosures in the Tehsil Office, Kothapeta. Further, there is a typed petition filed in this case which contains the recommendation of the Village Munsif and the recommendation of Revenue Inspector-P.W.4. It is not marked by prosecution. To support a conviction U/s. 467 IPC, there must be evidence that the document is a false document, within the meaning of section 464 IPC and that it was forged by the accused with some intent mentioned in sec. 463 IPC. It is not sufficient that some possible intent may be inferred from the facts, it is necessary such intent should be established by evidence, which is lacking in this case. Under Sec. 420 IPC, there must be evidence that the person deceived delivered to someone, or consented that some person shall retain certain property, that the person deceived was induced by the accused to do as above, that such person

was likely to cause damage or harm to that person in property. There must also evidence of fraudulent or dishonest intention at the time of the omission of the act in respect of which the cheating is alleged. Since the main part of the alleged signatures of P.W.4 and Village Munsif, Merlapalem (who is no more are completely torn and Ex.P1 is in such a condition that the Tahsildar, Kothapeta would not have been acted upon it in granting patta of the tamarind tree to the petitioner i.e., P.W.1. Therefore the question of commission of offences of cheating and thereby dishonestly inducing delivery of property, forgery of a valuable security or authority to make transfer any valuable security and using a genuine a forged document which is known to be forged are not proved against the accused, beyond all reasonable doubt.

In the result, the accused is given the benefit of doubt. The accused is found not guilty of the offences punishable Under sections 420, 467 and 471 IPC. and he is acquitted Under sec. 248(1) Cr.P.C.

Dictated to the Shorthand-writer, transcribed by him, Corrected by me and pronounced in Open Court on this the 27th day of November, 1979 in the presence of the accused.

Sd.D.Venkata Narayana, 27.11
Judicial Magistrate of the
1st Class, Kothapeta.

Appendix of evidence.
Witnesses examined for.

Prosecution:

P.W.1: Relangi Rattamma
P.W.2: Pericherla Satyanarayanaraju.
P.W.3: T.V.Sriramachandra Murty.
P.W.4: Malladi Panduranga Vithal,
RI, Atreyapuram.
P.W.5: K.M.Meera Sahe,
HC 1625, Ravulapalem P.S.
P.W.6: T.B.Pundarikakshudu,
Inspector of Police,
Ravulapalem.
P.W.7: P.Subba Rao,
Tahsildar, Kothapeta.

Defence:

None.

Documents marked:

- Ex.P1: Forged petition, dt. 10.7.77 of P.W.1
- Ex.P2: Slip
- Ex.P3: Statement of accused. Nil.
- Ex.P4: Statement of P.W.1
- Ex.P5: F.I.R. in Cr.No. 53/77.
- Ex.P6: Petition forwarded by the Tahsildar, Kothapeta to the S.H.O. Ravulapalem.

M.Os marked:

Nil.

Sd. D. Venkatanarayana
27.11.79
Judicial Magistrate of I Class
Kothapeta.

-/true copy/-

J. F. C. MAGISTRATE
KOTHAPETA.

EB
25/11/79

CALENDAR AND JUDGMENT
IN THE COURT OF THE JUDICIAL MAGISTRATE OF THE I CLASS
KOTHAPETA.

C.C.No. 13/79.

Date of:
Offence: 2 weeks prior to
21.7.77
Complaint: 1.2.79
Apprhn. of accused: 13.2.79.
Release on bail: 13.2.79.

Commencement of trial: 2.4.79
Close of trial: 20.11.79.
Sentence/Order: 27.11.79
The presiding officer is on CL
from 22.11.79 to 24.11.79 and is
on permission on 25.11.79).

Explanation for the delay and remarks: The delay is due to
non-production of witnesses by the complainant.

Complainant: The S.H.O. Ravulapalem Cr.No.53/79.

Name of accused. Father's name. Age. Religion. Calling Village Taluk

Irlapati Gangadha-
ra Rao. Pullayya 19 Hindu Mazdoor Merla- Kotha-
palem. peta

Offence: Under Sec. 420, 467 and 471 IPC.

Finding: Not guilty.

Sentence/Order: The accused is acquitted U/s 248(1) Cr.P.C.
of the offence Under Sec. 420, 467 and 471 IPC.

Sd. D. Venkata Narayana
27.11.1979
Judl. Magistrate of the 1st class
Kothapeta.

-/true copy/-

J. F. C. MAGISTRATE
KOTHAPETA.

25/8/79

IN THE GRAM PANCHAYAT OF THE MERLAPALEM VILLAGE
CERTIFYING DECISION P.R.NO.87
ON THE 13th DAY OF DECEMBER, 1988.
PARTICULARS OF GANGADHARA RAO IRLAPATI

This is to certify that the particulars of Gangadhara Rao Irlapati which are given below:-

<p><u>FAMILY PARTICULARS</u> Name: Gangadhara Rao Sir name: Irlapati Father's Name: Pullayya Place of Birth: Merlapalem Date of Birth: 25th, May, 1958</p> <p><u>NATIVITY PARTICULARS</u> Nativity of Village: Merlapalem Mandal : Atreyapuram District: East Godavari State : Andhra Pradesh</p> <p><u>COMMUNITY PARTICULARS</u> Caste: Scheduled Caste Sub-Caste: Mala Religion: Hindu Nationality: Indian Social Position: Poor Social conduct: Good Patriot</p>	<p><u>ACADEMICAL PARTICULARS</u> Scientific qualification: None, Natural Genius General Education Elementary School Study: 1 to 5 classes Upper Primary School study: 6 to 7 classes High School Study: 8 to 10 classes Pre-University course: Intermediate Graduation: B.A. (Arts) Post-Graduation: Technical: F.T. (Trysem)</p> <p><u>RESEARCH EXPERIENCE PARTICULARS</u> Year of starting of researches: 1963 Year of continuing of researches: 1988 Name of the research: Theory of Universe (1977) Place of the research: Irlapati Merlapalem Results of research: Geographical Studies Total Period of his service: He has sacrificed his life to the country for 25 years</p> <p><u>PRESENT SITUATION PARTICULARS</u> Occupation: Un-employee Wealth: Poverty Health: Illness</p>
---	--

The above particulars are true and correct as per the enquiry, verification and written witness of senior adults of the Gram Sabha.

గ్రామ పంచాయతీ అధ్యక్షుడు
పెద్దపాటె. (మెర్లపాలెం)

Signature: *[Handwritten Signature]*
Designation: **GRAM PANCHAYAT**
MERLAPALEM

48

06

171

☪ ☪ [Regd. No. 431 of 1988]
[People's Action For Rural Awakening]

PARA
RAVULAPALEM
533 238
E.G.Dt., A.P.

Date 5th Oct. '93

SERVICE CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that MR.GANGADHARA RAO IRLAPATI
MERLAPALEM VILLAGE
ATRYAPURAM MANDAL
EAST GODAVARI DT.

was associated with our organisation on a voluntary basis.
He was active in the field of remedial education helping with
literacy programmes and in general taking an active part in
issues that concerned the greater good of the community.
He was steadfast and reliable.
He was with us from October '88 to May '93.

Thomas Pallithanam

Thomas Pallithanam
Advocate
Director
People's Action For Rural Awakening
Ravulapalem

**DIRECTOR
PARA
RAVULAPALEM**

36
Vikram University

UJJAIN 456 010, INDIA

Dr. Sanjay K. Ghosh
Professor
School of Studies in Physics

Tel office : 91-734-551222
Residence: 91-734-551971
Fax : 91-734-552076

e-mail: *drsanjayghosh*
@hotmail.com

12.7.2000

Shri G. R. Irlapati
C/O Shri K. Chiranjeevi
H. No. 28-29
Saibabanagar, Jeedimetla
Hyderabad-5

Dear Shri Irlapati,

Received your letter along with a copy of your proposed hypothetical model of cosmology. You have requested me to make comments on it. I have gone through your model and found that you have quite systematically developed your logic.

With regards,

Yours sincerely,

(Sanjay K. Ghosh)

Residence : 137, Agrasen Nagar, Mangal Colony, UJJAIN 456 010, INDIA

Professor G. D. Baruah,

DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS
DIBRUGARH UNIVERSITY
DIBRUGARH - 786 004 (INDIA)

Telephone : (0373) - (70224)
Fax : (0373) - (70323)
R (0373) - 70 654

Ref. No. _____

Date _____

Aug 28, 2000

G. R. URLAPATI,
H. No. 5-30-4/I,
Sai Baba Nagar, I.D.A. Jeedimetla,
Hyderabad - 500 055.

Dear Urlapati,

Received your recent letter (dated nil) addressed to me and to my research student and also your proposed hypothesis regarding the external universe. I have noted with pleasure that you have also invented some devices for predicting natural events like cyclones, earthquakes etc. Your efforts are praise-worthy. After all we have to do something for the benefit of mankind.

As regards your hypothesis many things should be elaborated. Recent developments in astrophysics etc. should be taken into consideration. It is true that even persons like Warlikar has some reservation about the big bang theory. Even some nobel laureate like Townes are talking about what happened before big bang etc. So you can also appreciate that we have also limitations. Please continue with your effort.

President
Section of Physics

Yours sincerely
G. D. Baruah

85th Indian Science Congress
HYDERABAD

- 35 -

From:
The Director,
U.P.State Observatory,
Manora Peak,
Naini Tal.

To,
Mr. G.R.IRLAPATI,
H.No. 5-30-4/I,
Sai Baba Nagar,
IDA, Jeedimelta,
Hydrabad-500 055

No. 0/ 1707 /Misc

Date 21 Oct., 2000

Dear Irlapati,

Your letter dated NIL was received on 10-10-2000. As regards my comments on your paper entitled "A NEW HYPOTHETICAL MODEL OF COSMOLOGY", I can only submit that till date no theory exists which can explain both Microscopic as well as Macroscopic universe. To me your hypothesis appears to be your efforts in that direction. I appreciate your endeavour. Keep it up.

Yours,

(B.S.Rautela)
Assistant Astronomer
for Director

c:\w\k\irlapati

34

Prof. L. K. SINGH
HEAD, PHYSICS & ELECTRO.
Dr. R. M. L. AVADH UNIV.
FAIZABAD
224001

श्री राममनोहर लोहिया अवध विश्वविद्यालय फैजाबाद

05278-45230 814230
दूरभाष : 812057
813386
फैक्स संख्या : 0527/814230

क : लो. वि. / Phys/Lk/12/10/2000

दिनांक... 10/10/2000

Dear Mr. RLAPATI,

I received your letter and manuscript of your hypothetical model on cosmology. I congratulate you for your great effort and I wish you a successful future. I went through the manuscript and found it very nice and praiseworthy.

My wishes are with you.

Yours

Sincerely yours
L. K. Singh